

Supporting Information

Fluorescent Supramolecular Gels based on D-Sorbitol Derivatives

Emmanuel Odella, Miryam Criado-Gonzalez, Rodrigo A. Ponzio, David Mecerreyes, Matías L. Picchio and Daniele Mantione**

E. Odella, R. A. Ponzio.

Instituto de Investigaciones en Tecnologías Energéticas y Materiales Avanzados (IITEMA), Universidad Nacional de Río Cuarto (UNRC), Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas (CONICET). Río Cuarto X5804BYA, Córdoba, Argentina.

M., Criado-Gonzalez.

Institute of Polymer Science and Technology (ICTP-CSIC). Juan de la Cierva 3, 28006 Madrid, Spain.

M. L., Picchio.

POLYMAT, Department of Mining-Metallurgy Engineering and Materials Science, School of Engineering, University of the Basque Country (UPV/ EHU). Plaza Torres Quevedo 1, 48013 Bilbao, Spain.

M. L., Picchio, D., Mantione, D., Mecerreyes.

IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science. Plaza Euskadi 5, 48009 Bilbao, Spain.

matiasluis.picchiop@ehu.es, daniele.mantione@ehu.es.

D., Mantione, D., Mecerreyes.

POLYMAT, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU. Avenida Tolosa 72, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain.

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1. Materials

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and BLDpharm and used without any further purification. Solvents were obtained from Fisher. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was executed with silica gel-coated glass plates from Merck Millipore.

2. Synthesis and Structural Characterization

The synthesis of the new low molecular weight gelators (LMWGs) was achieved following standard and reported procedures. The general synthetic approach for the preparation of 1-(2,6-di(naphthalen-2-yl)tetrahydro-[1,3]dioxino[5,4-d][1,3]dioxin-4-yl)ethane-1,2-diol (DNapS), 1-(2,6-bis(benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)tetrahydro-[1,3]dioxino[5,4-d][1,3]dioxin-4-yl)ethane-1,2-diol (DBTDS), and 6-(5-hydroxy-4-(1,2,3-trihydroxypropyl)-1,3-dioxan-2-yl)-2H-chromen-2-one (MCumS) is shown in Figure 1a.

1-(2,6-bis(benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazol-4-yl)tetrahydro-[1,3]dioxino[5,4-d][1,3]dioxin-4-yl)ethane-1,2-diol (DBTDS)

The synthesis of DBTDS was carried out following a slightly modified procedure, given the diacetal compound after purification.^[1,2] 616 mg of D-sorbitol (1.0 eq.) were transferred into a round-bottomed flask, and 6 mL of dry MeOH were added. The white suspension was then stirred at room temperature. A solution of Benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (1 g, 1.8 eq.) and 4-TSA (450 mg, 0.7 eq.) in 3 mL of MeOH was added dropwise to the D-sorbitol suspension and the mixture was stirred for 48 h. The resulting precipitate was filtered under reduced pressure and washed with a small amount of dry MeOH to afford 257 mg of DBTDS (18 % yield). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃), δ (ppm): 8.07-7.88 (m, 4H), 7.69-7.54 (m, 2H), 6.43 (s, 1H), 6.31 (s, 1H), 4.59 (d, *J* = 12.8 Hz, 1H), 4.50 (s, 1H), 4.38 (dd, *J* = 12.9, 2.3 Hz, 1H), 4.29 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 4.18 (s, 1H), 4.05-3.94 (m, 1H), 3.86 (dd, *J* = 11.6, 3.2 Hz, 1H), 3.78 (dd, *J* = 11.6, 4.7 Hz, 1H), 2.34 (br, 1H), 1.66 (br, 1H). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 64.0, 69.8, 70.5, 70.5, 71.1, 78.0, 96.9, 97.7, 122.4, 122.4, 126.6, 127.0, 129.4, 129.4, 129.8, 129.9, 152.5, 152.7, 155.1, 155.3. HRMS *m/z* calc. [M+Na]⁺ 497.0560; exp. 497.0564.

1-(2,6-di(naphthalen-2-yl)tetrahydro-[1,3]dioxino[5,4-d][1,3]dioxin-4-yl)ethane-1,2-diol
(DNapS)

The synthesis of DNapS was carried out following a slightly modified procedure, given the diacetal compound after purification.^[1,2] 648 mg of D-sorbitol (1.0 eq.) were transferred into a round-bottomed flask, and 6 mL of dry MeOH were added. The white suspension was then stirred at room temperature. A solution of 2-Naphthaldehyde (1 g, 1.8 eq.) and 4-toluene sulfonic acid (4-TSA) (473.5 mg, 0.7 eq.) in 3 mL of MeOH was added dropwise to the D-sorbitol suspension, and the mixture was stirred overnight. The resulting precipitate was filtered under reduced pressure and washed several times with MeOH to afford 940 mg of DNapS (58 % yield). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm): 8.03-7.89 (m, 8H), 7.69-7.59 (m, 2H), 7.53 (dd, *J* = 6.3, 3.2 Hz, 4H), 5.87 (s, 2H), 4.91 (br, 1H), 4.45 (br, 1H), 4.35-4.22 (m, 3H), 4.06 (s, 1H), 3.96 (d, *J* = 10.9 Hz, 1H), 3.87 (br, 1H), 3.66 (d, *J* = 10.2 Hz, 1H), 3.50 (dd, *J* = 11.2, 5.2 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm): 62.7, 67.7, 68.7, 69.4, 70.3, 77.8, 99.4, 99.5, 124.2, 124.3, 125.0, 125.1, 126.2, 126.3, 126.3, 126.4, 127.6, 127.7, 128.2, 132.3, 133.0, 133.0, 135.9, 136.2. HRMS *m/z* calc. [M+H]⁺ 459.1802; exp. 459.1802.

6-(5-hydroxy-4-(1,2,3-trihydroxypropyl)-1,3-dioxan-2-yl)-2H-chromen-2-one (MCumS)

The synthesis of MCumS was carried out following a slightly modified procedure given the monoacetal compound after purification.^[1,2] 174 mg of D-sorbitol (1.0 eq.) were transferred into a round-bottomed flask, and 3 mL of dry MeOH were added. The white suspension was then stirred at room temperature. A solution of 2-Oxo-2H-chromene-6-carbaldehyde (299 mg, 1.8 eq.) and 4-TSA (127 mg, 0.7 eq.) in 6 mL of MeOH was added dropwise to the D-sorbitol suspension, and the mixture was stirred overnight. The resulting precipitate was filtered under reduced pressure and washed several times with dry MeOH to give 233 mg of the mono acetal MCumS (72 % yield). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm): 8.10

(d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.83 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.73 (dd, $J = 8.6, 2.1$ Hz, 1H), 7.40 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 1H), 6.50 (d, $J = 9.5$ Hz, 1H), 5.64 (s, 1H), 4.75-4.63 (m, 2H), 4.48-4.36 (m, 2H), 3.85 (t, $J = 6.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.78-3.66 (m, 3H), 3.64-3.52 (m, 3H), 3.47-3.37 (m, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 60.9, 61.5, 62.7, 69.1, 79.4, 81.0, 99.1, 115.9, 116.3, 118.2, 126.3, 130.3, 135.2, 144.3, 153.5, 159.9. HRMS m/z calc. $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ 339.1074; exp. 339.1081.

3. Methods and Characterization

Preparation of deep eutectic solvents (DES). Hydrophobic DES based on thymol: betaine (Thy: Bet, 4: 1 mole ratio) and thymol: menthol (Thy: Men, 1: 2 mole ratio) were prepared by mixing the solid components at 90 °C under stirring until a clear liquid was obtained.

Preparation of supramolecular organogels, hydrogels, and eutectogels. Organogels and hydrogels were prepared using a simple heating/cooling procedure. 10 mg of the LMWG was weighed into a sample vial, and 1 mL of the selected solvent was added. The mixture was sonicated for 5 minutes, then heated to approximately 10 °C below the solvent's boiling point and subsequently allowed to cool to room temperature. Eutectogels were obtained by solubilizing the LMWGs in the corresponding DES during heating. For eutectogels formed in Thy:Bet DES, 30 mg of MCumS was solubilized in 1 mL Thy:Bet by heating at 120 °C for 2 h, followed by a cooling step up to room temperature. For eutectogels formed in Thy:Men DES, 30 mg of MCumS was solubilized in 1 mL DES by heating at 175 °C for 4 h, followed by a cooling step up to room temperature. The Vial inversion test was used to infer the formation of the supramolecular gels.

NMR characterization. NMR experiments were performed using a Bruker Avance DPX 300 spectrometer at 300 MHz employing standard pulse techniques. Solvents such as CDCl_3 and DMSO- d_6 were chosen for the experiments, which were performed at room temperature.

Mass spectrometry. High resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) has been measured by direct injection in a Waters modelo SYNAPTTM G2 HDMSTM, using a Q-TOF detector and positive electrospray ionization ESI+.

ATR-FTIR measurements. ATR-FTIR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Alpha II spectrophotometer employing a Platinum ATR module with a diamond window. All spectra were collected in the range 4000-500 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 64 scans.

Steady-state spectroscopy. Steady-state fluorescence spectra were measured using a Horiba FluoroMax Plus spectrofluorometer and corrected for the detection system response. For solution-state measurements, a 1 cm path length quartz cuvette was employed, with LMWGs dissolved at a concentration of 2×10^{-5} M in each solvent. For gel-state experiments, a small portion of the supramolecular gel was carefully mounted on a clean glass microscope slide. The slide was positioned on a solid-sample holder accessory provided by the instrument, and the sample was oriented at 60° relative to the excitation beam. Experiments with DNapS/toluene, DBTDS/EtOAc, and MCumS/water gels were performed at 1 % w/v, while MCumS/Thy:Bet gels were investigated at 3 % w/v.

SAXS measurements. Small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) data were collected on a SAXSpoint 5.0 instrument (Anton Paar) at room temperature. Gels were prepared as described above and immediately transferred, while hot, into 1.92 mm diameter capillaries (MicroLumen), which were then sealed to prevent solvent evaporation during measurement. Primux 100 micro microfocus was employed as the X-ray source ($\text{Cu K}\alpha = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). The scattering intensities were detected using a 2D EIGER2 R and PILATUS4 R series HPC detectors. The sample-detector distance was set at 1622 mm, thus resulting in a q [$q=4\pi\sin(\theta/2)/\lambda$] range of 0.003 to 0.2 \AA^{-1} . The 2D scattering patterns were azimuthally averaged to obtain 1D profiles. Background subtraction was performed by subtracting the scattering of a capillary containing the corresponding pure solvent. The data were fitted in the SasView 6.1.2 software package.^[3] A linear combination of power law with either flexible (FC) or flexible cylinder elliptical (FCE) models was used (see section S8).^[4,5] These models describe the gel fibres as flexible worm-like chains composed of cylindrical Kuhn segments, providing a physically meaningful representation of their semiflexible nature. Moreover, they have been successfully applied to describe the structure of other low-molecular weight gels.^[5,6] X-ray scattering length densities (SLDs) for all samples were calculated by means of the NIST neutron activation and scattering calculator.^[7]

SEM microscopy. Before observation, the solvent was removed from the gels. For MCumS hydrogel, the sample intended for SEM analysis was prepared by first subjecting it to freeze-drying in liquid nitrogen, followed by lyophilizing it overnight. Under this procedure, the resultant soft material is designated as a cryogel. In the case of DBTDS/ethyl acetate, DBTDS/ethanol, DNapS/toluene organogels, and MCumS/Thy:Bet and MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogels, a portion of the gels were left to dry under ambient pressure overnight to give the xerogels. The remaining

sample (cryogel or xerogels) was then coated with a thin layer of gold vapor by means of a BioRad Sputter Coater SC 500 at 25 mA and ~10 Pa for 30 s. Finally, the SEM images were obtained on a TM3030 series Hitachi Tabletop Microscope using 15 kV accelerating voltage.

XRD measurements. X-ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded using an XRDynamic 500 diffractometer (Anton Paar) operating in Bragg–Brentano geometry at room temperature. The as-prepared gels were spread onto a glass slide as a thin film and allowed to dry in air prior to data collection. The current and voltage of the X-ray source generator (Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) were set to 50 mA and 40 kV, respectively. The samples were measured over a 2θ range from 3° to 60° with a scanning rate of 109 s per step. The data were processed and analyzed using the XRDynamic 500 software package. The d-spacing values were calculated using Bragg's law ($n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta$).

Rheology measurements. Rheological measurements were performed using an AR-G2 rheometer (TA Instruments) with a stainless-steel plate geometry of 25 mm diameter. Strain sweeps were conducted from 0.01 to 1000% at 1 Hz and 25 °C, and frequency sweeps from 0.01 to 10 Hz at 1% strain. Dynamic step strain recovery tests were performed by varying the applied strain between 1 and 1000% at 1 Hz and 25 °C for short times (120 s) to demonstrate the self-recovery and injectability properties.

Circular Dichroism measurements. The circular dichroism data have been recorded on a Jasco J-1500 equipped with a Xe lamp, using a 2 mm path length, and recording from 200 to 700 nm at interval of 1 nm at 2000 mdeg/1,0 dOD and 100nm/min. The baselines have been performed and set up in triplicates. All CD data are presented as ellipticity and recorded in millidegree (mdeg).

4. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Data

Compound DBTDS

Figure S1. 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum of DBTDS in CDCl₃.

Figure S2. 75 MHz ¹³C NMR spectrum of DBTDS in CDCl₃.

Compound DNapS

Figure S3. 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum of DNapS in DMSO-*d*₆.

Figure S4. 75 MHz ¹³C NMR spectrum of DNapS in DMSO-*d*₆.

Compound MCumS

Figure S5. 300 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum of MCumS in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Figure S6. 75 MHz ^{13}C NMR spectrum of MCumS in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

5. Circular Dichroism Analysis

Circular dichroism (CD) measurements have been performed for MCumS/water as representative and most used system. The CD spectra (Figure S7) reveal clear differences between the solution and gel states, indicating significant reorganization upon gelation. In solution, a moderate positive CD band is observed at 335 nm, together with a weaker signal at shorter wavelengths. In the gel state, the CD intensity increases markedly (approximately threefold) and exhibits a slight bathochromic shift. This amplification indicates enhanced chiral ordering in the assembled state.

The absorption spectra further support this conclusion. While the solution state of MCumS/water displays relatively well-defined bands below 330 nm, the gel state exhibits band broadening and a more gradual decrease at longer wavelengths. These changes are consistent with increased intermolecular interactions and a modified electronic environment in the self-assembled state.

Figure S7. CD and Absorption spectra of MCumS/water in solution (Sol, left panels) and in gel (Gel, right panels) states.

6. Rheological Analysis

Figure S8. Storage modulus (G' , solid squares) and loss modulus (G'' , hollow squares) of DNapS/toluene organogel as a function of the (a) oscillation strain at 1 Hz and (b) frequency at 1% strain. (c) Dynamic step-strain amplitude tests of DNapS/toluene organogel. G' (solid squares) and G'' (hollow squares) of DBTDS/EtOAc organogel as a function of the (d) oscillation strain at 1 Hz and (e) frequency at 1% strain. (f) Dynamic step-strain amplitude tests of DBTDS/EtOAc organogel.

Figure S9. Storage modulus (G' , solid squares) and loss modulus (G'' , hollow squares) of MCumS/water hydrogel as a function of the (a) oscillation strain at 1 Hz and (b) frequency at 1% strain.

7. Steady-State Fluorescence Data

Figure S10. Normalized fluorescence spectra of MCumS/Thy:Bet in both solution and gel states ($\lambda_{\text{exc}}=440$ nm).

8. SAXS Analysis

The SAXS scattering profiles were fitted by models which combine a power law (PL) with either a flexible cylinder (FC) or a flexible cylinder elliptical (FCE) form factor $P(q)_i$,^[8,9] according to equation S1:

$$I(q) = SF_O(SF_{PL}P(q)_{PL} + SF_iP(q)_i) + background \quad \text{equation S1}$$

where i represents either the FC or FCE form factors. SF_O , SF_{PL} and SF_i are the overall, power law and form factor scale factors, respectively. The background accounts for the incoherent background scattering from the sample and was optimized and fixed to a constant value during the fitting. This approach minimizes parameter correlation and improves fit stability without affecting the extracted structural parameters. The parameters describing the FC model are: the length of the flexible cylinder, the radius of the flexible cylinder, and the Kuhn length (b) which is related to the persistence length ($b=2l_p$) and usually employed to describe the stiffness of the flexible cylinder.^[8,9] Similarly, the parameters describing the FCE model are the same as those of the FC model, but additionally include the axis ratio (major radius/minor radius) to account for the

elliptical cross section of the flexible cylinder. The SF_0 was arbitrary set at 1 during the fitting procedure. The results of the fits are summarized in Table S1.

Table S1. The model fit parameters obtained by fitting the experimental SAXS data with the combined power law and either flexible cylinder or flexible cylinder elliptical models.

	DNapS/toluene	DBTDS/EtOAc	MCumS/water	MCumS/Thy:Men
Model	Flexible cylinder + power law	Flexible cylinder elliptical + power law	Flexible cylinder elliptical + power law	Flexible cylinder elliptical + power law
Background^a	0.005 cm ⁻¹	0.006 cm ⁻¹	0.003 cm ⁻¹	0.0007 cm ⁻¹
SF_i	(1.070 ± 0.032) × 10 ⁻³	(1.73 ± 0.39) × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.58 ± 0.04) × 10 ⁻⁴	(8.16 ± 0.09) × 10 ⁻⁴
Length^b	> 3000 Å	> 3000 Å	> 3000 Å	> 3000 Å
Kuhn Length	119 ± 11 Å	57 ± 17 Å	166.2 ± 7.6 Å	200.4 ± 1.7 Å
Radius	36.7 ± 0.7 Å	25.1 ± 1.8 Å	50.5 ± 0.5 Å	11.05 ± 0.07 Å
Axis Ratio	NA	3.2 ± 0.3	2.81 ± 0.03	30.8 ± 0.2
SLD gelator^c	13 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²	12.5 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²	10.5 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²	10.5 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²
SLD solvent^c	7.98 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²	8.30 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²	9.46 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²	8.80 × 10 ⁻⁶ Å ²
SF_{PL}	(1.2 ± 0.9) × 10 ⁻⁶	(1.2 ± 0.6) × 10 ⁻⁹	(3.5 ± 0.5) × 10 ⁻⁶	(4.52 ± 0.04) × 10 ⁻⁴
Exponent Power Law	2.97 ± 0.13	4.28 ± 0.09	3.07 ± 0.02	2.657 ± 0.002
χ_{red}²	1.37	1.62	1.72	2.45

^a A constant background was fixed during fitting based on the intensity plateau observed at the high q-vector.

^b The cylinder length was assumed to be larger than the length scales accessible within the experimental SAXS q-range and therefore cannot be reliably determined.

^c Calculated by means of the NIST neutron activation and scattering calculator (ref. [7]).

Figure S11. SAXS profiles for MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel. The experimental data are shown as filled circles and the model fit as solid line.

9. XRD Data

Figure S12. XRD diffraction pattern of MCumS/Thy:Men xerogel.

10. References

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